

Exploring the Potential of Generating Renewable Energy from Daily Producing Wastes

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Abstract Food waste processing and disposal issues have a negative impact on public health and the environment. One method of getting rid of food waste is to dump it on land, but when rainwater falls on it, it creates toxic leachate. One of the most important ways to address the issue of food waste and meet the need for energy is to reuse food waste for the production of biodiesel. A study was conducted to explore the possibilities of bio-energy production through anaerobic digestion utilizing food wastes collected from an educational campus in Coimbatore region. This study not only enhances existing research on waste-to-energy solutions but also establishes the foundation for possible applications of AD technology in particular circumstances.

Keywords Food waste, bio-energy, anaerobic digestion, hostel waste.

Introduction

Food waste comprises non-utilization of edibles (Tsang et. al. 2019) in addition to the incorrect use of valuable resources consumed for their production, thereby degrading the environmental quality (Mishra et. al. 2020). By 2050, world's population is projected to increase by ten billion, which will significantly increase the global food demand and destabilize the global food-supply scenario (Haldar et. al. 2022). According to a research, over 1.3 Giga tonnes of food, valued at 750 billion dollars, are wasted annually worldwide (FAO 2017). India, home to more than 1.3 billion people, generates 0.5 kg/day of organic garbage daily per person (FAO 2017). In India, a large quantity of food waste is generated from the restaurants, grocery stores, lodging facilities, retail establishments, airline cafeterias, and the food manufacturing sector. The per capita generation of food waste (kg/year) in the country is in the range of 90, 68 and 63 among the high, middle- and poor-income groups respectively according to United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) Food Waste Index report 2021 (Chaudhary et. al. 2021). Due to the standard food waste management procedures, an enormous volume of food and kitchen waste is accumulated each year (Sharma et. al. 2021). Food waste produced per year equals 1.4 billion hectares of cultivable land which is approximately 28% of all agricultural land on earth (Paritosh et. al. 2017; Sharma et. al. 2021). Food waste management is one of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), which focuses on reducing the global food waste by fifty percent from the farm to fork within 2030 (United Nations 2015). This objective is predicated on a thorough comprehension of the detrimental effects of food loss and waste, which include the needless use of energy, water, and land as well as the production of greenhouse gas emissions (N.r.v.nen et.al. 2020). Understanding the characteristics of food waste is necessary in order to comprehend the difficulties associated with managing it (Dutta et. al. 2021; Davison et.al. 2022). Mostly, food waste is composed of proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, and trace amounts of inorganic compounds (Paritosh et. al. 2017). The characterization of food waste, in terms of its moisture content, pH, carbon and nitrogen content, moisture and volatile solids, show significant variability (Abo et.al. 2019). Vegetable and rice-based food waste is high in carbohydrates, while meat and egg-based food waste is high in proteins and fats. Food waste has high carbohydrate content, making it suitable as a feedstock (Smithers 2008) for butanol fermentation. Whey, apple pomace, and potato peels are excellent substrates (Kosmala et. al. 2011) for butanol fermentation due to their high carbohydrate content (Li et. al. 2015). 84% of the weight of restaurant, kitchen, and other food waste is made up of water, with solids making up the remaining 16% (Kim et. al. 2017). It was observed that food waste from different sources usually had different compositional characteristics. A comparison analysis had been carried out to determine the characteristic variations among five different types of food waste, including kitchen garbage. (Ho and Chu 2019). The home food waste had the highest protein level of about 26% (Haldar et.al. 2022). To investigate the potential for converting everyday food waste materials into renewable energy sources rather than dumping them in landfills (Barik et.al. 2018), this study delves into the intriguing realm of anaerobic digestion (AD), a natural process used to unlock the hidden energy potential within organic waste streams. AD replicates the natural decomposition process, but under controlled settings in sealed and no oxygen environments (Uddin and Wright 2023). A ranged microbial consortium grows within these digesters, feeding on organic matter and producing biogas as a byproduct. This biogas, which is mostly made of approximately 60% methane (CH₄) and 40% carbon dioxide (CO₂), provides a diverse fuel source for electricity generation, heating, and transportation, helping to create a cleaner and more sustainable energy landscape (Wilkie 2005). Likewise, this study formed a specific collection plan targeting three distinct sources: Fruit and vegetable waste from markets, hostel mess wastes and food court wastes from the college campus in Coimbatore. Furthermore, through the analysis of biogas production and composition, we are looking to unlock the hidden energy potential within these everyday discards, which will not only contribute to the growing body of waste-to-energy solutions but will also pave the way for potential AD technology implementation in these specific contexts, transforming waste into a valuable resource and contributing to a greener future.

Materials and Methods

Feedstock Collection

Three distinct locations were targeted for waste collection: Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College (SREC) food court waste; hostel mess waste (SREC) and fruit and vegetable wastes from Palamudir Nilayam - Coimbatore. The objective of this comprehensive approach was to encompass the varied composition and generation patterns of food waste in Coimbatore. Diverse samples of fruit and vegetable wastes were collected daily from the above designated points for 1 week, with their kind permission and knowledge. This approach ensured a comprehensive representation of the store's waste profile, encompassing the entire range of fruits and vegetables wasted and assuring the inclusion of a diverse sample. It was possible to get straight access to SREC's food waste through cooperation with their hostel mess. In order to provide controls for dietary variations, samples were gathered during breakfast, lunch, and dinner over the course of 1 week. Food waste remained uncontaminated by utensils or packaging materials due to careful classification. In the same manner as the hostel mess, food refuse from the SREC food court canteen was collected directly from the disposal area. For the same duration of 1 week, samples were gathered from a variety of food vendors and during various mealtimes in order to represent a wide range of food categories and patterns of waste generation in the food court. During the collection process, thorough hygiene rules were followed to keep the trash streams clean and free of contamination. With this multifaceted method, a large and accurate sample set was obtained, allowing for a thorough investigation into the viability of producing renewable energy from a wide range of waste materials, thereby creating a greener future.

Feedstock Preparation

Upon collection, each waste stream was carefully prepared to maintain consistency and homogeneity for subsequent analysis. Visual inspection was performed to detect any visible non-biodegradable items in the samples, as the collected samples had a wide range of organic matter including fruit peels, vegetable trimmings, food preparation residues, disposable plates, packing materials, and other foreign materials. Following that, the materials were cut into smaller pieces with a laboratory blender to ensure a uniform particle size and combination. The moisture content was evaluated by oven drying the 3 types of samples at 105°C for 24 hours (Patricia Cunniff and Association of Official Analytical Chemists 1995). The dried materials were then ground into a fine powder with a laboratory mill for further analysis (Sluiter et. al. 2008).

Methodology

To investigate the biogas production potential of our collected waste streams, we used a well-known and promising AD process (Obileke et. al. 2023). This oxygen-free condition enables bacteria to degrade organic materials and produce biogas, which is largely constituted of methane (CH₄), and CO₂, and other minor gases (Wilkie 2005). To ensure uniformity, two identical lab-scale anaerobic digesters of 10 liters each, with a headspace of 1 liter and a useable space of 9 liters, were meticulously designed for each waste stream. To replicate the real-world circumstances often seen in waste treatment facilities, operational parameters were carefully managed to maintain mesophilic conditions with temperatures ranging from 35 to 40°C (Almeida Streitwieser 2017). AD sludge from a nearby wastewater treatment plant was used as the inoculum, resulting in a diverse microbial consortium capable of degrading organic materials. The digester was fitted with a continuous stirrer to maintain homogeneity and to improve mass transfer inside the digester. Each waste stream (fruit and vegetable waste, hostel food waste, food court waste) and inoculum were subjected to proximate analysis, which included volatile solids, total solids, and moisture contents. Furthermore, the dried samples were evaluated to meet the required organic loading rate (3g VS/L/day) for 20 days (Yulin Ye 2013). Daily feeding with prepared substrates maintained the desired OLR. Maintaining ideal conditions for AD was essential; continuous monitoring and adjustment of pH and alkalinity levels guaranteed process stability. The digester's functioning was regularly checked using a gas flow meter. Following the digestion duration, the gas composition (CH₄ and CO₂) was analyzed using gas chromatography.

Results and Discussion

The mass of the substrates, SREC food court- food waste, SREC hostel mess waste, and food and vegetable waste from the store, weighing 179.52g, 143.77g, and 130.94g, respectively, were utilized as the feedstock after the computation as per Dhar et al. (2016). Table 1 summarizes the results of volatile solids (VS), total solids (TS), and moisture content of various food waste streams, including SREC hostel mess waste, SREC food court food waste, and food and vegetable waste from store.

Table 1. Proximate Analysis Results

Waste Stream	VS (%)	TS (%)	MC(%)
SREC Hostel Mess Wastes	81.67	15.04	83
Fruit and Vegetable Store wastes	72.96	20.62	74
SREC Food Court Wastes	76.42	18.78	78

The biogas yield (Fig.1) for the various waste streams investigated varied considerably, as demonstrated by the outcomes of the biogas production experiments. The waste materials from the SREC Hostel Mess exhibited the greatest biogas production, yielding a phenomenal 830 ml/g of VS. The findings indicate that the hostel mess residues contain organic materials that are extremely susceptible to AD, possibly as a result of their distinctive composition and properties. Hostel mess wastes generally comprise a wide variety of food residues, such as food preparation remnants and leftovers. These materials offer abundant organic content that microorganisms can decompose and convert into biogas. Subsequently, the SREC Food Court Wastes demonstrated a significant rate of biogas generation, approximately 650 ml/g of VS. Although this result is comparatively lower than the waste generated by the hostel mess, it still highlights the potential of utilizing food waste from food court canteens (Gandhi et.al. 2019) to generate renewable energy. It is probable that a considerable amount of organic matter suitable for anaerobic digestion is present in these wastes, although their composition may differ slightly from that of hostel mess wastes.

Fig.1. Biogas Production of all the 3 types of food waste

On the other hand, the biogas generation extracted from the residues of the Fruit and Vegetable Store was relatively modest, yielding around 600 ml/g of VS. While this result is still significant, it implies that the organic materials found in fruit and vegetable store wastes might be more difficult to access or less suitable for AD in comparison to food wastes originating from hostel messes and food court canteens. Moreover, methane production rates and biodegradability may be impacted by the protein content and the presence of particular organic compounds (Vidal et.al. 2000). Additional examination of the profiles of waste composition may provide insight into these possible contributors. It is important to mention that although VS content offers a reliable approximation of the organic matter accessible for digestion, biogas production can also be impacted by lignin content, particle size, and the existence of inhibitory compounds (Li et.al. 2017). Enhanced compositional analysis may provide additional understanding of the observed discrepancies. Overall, this study underscores the considerable capacity of SREC hostel mess residues to produce biogas, predominantly attributable to their elevated VS content. Additional research into the compositional intricacies of each waste stream and refinement of digester parameters may facilitate the generation of biogas from these varied sources in an even more efficient manner.

Conclusion

To conclude, this investigation into the possibility of converting various types of food waste into renewable energy has produced significant findings. Through the utilization of AD, it successfully unlocked the hidden potential within fruit and vegetable store waste, hostel mess food waste, and food court canteen waste. Moreover, this study supports the idea that AD isn't a "one-size-fits-all" solution; diverse waste streams exhibit distinct attributes that necessitate customized methodologies. Further exploration of microbial communities, optimization of digester conditions, and investigation into pre-treatment methods offer promising directions for future research aimed at uncovering the untapped environmentally friendly potential inherent in every wasted portion. Nevertheless, this study not only enhances existing research on waste-to-energy solutions (Ankur choudhary et.al. 2020) but also establishes the foundation for possible applications of AD technology in particular circumstances. For instance, Coimbatore, known to be the textile hub of

South India is generating approximately 1,300 metric tons of garbage daily. The rate of solid waste generation in Coimbatore is about 800 g per person/day which includes primarily house-hold wastes, and garbage collected from industrial organizations. As an industrial city of Tamil Nadu, Coimbatore has an area of 257.36 sq. km and a population of 1.8 million. The organization of the city is divided into five zones, each consisting of 100 wards. According to the City Municipal Corporation's data, more than 900 tons of solid wastes are collected from five million households daily, of which compostable percentage is 50%. The remaining percentage of the total waste finally reaches the mixed-waste landfill in Vellore. Only 50% of the city's organic waste is processed and the remaining percentage ends up in landfills. This results in a large amount of GHG emissions on account of methane, it is estimated that the sector is responsible for 500,000 tCO₂e of the city's GHG emission i.e., 17% of the total emissions in 2022. Recently, the city has planned to implement a bio CNG plant (150 TPD capacity) to process the organic fraction of the solid waste, which is expected to operate from February 2024. The project is aligned to Coimbatore city's Master Plan as well as Coimbatore Climate Action Plan. The project will result in significant reduction in Solid Waste Management expenditure of the city and would have wider climate and ecosystem benefits. It would reduce the Greenhouse emissions (GHG) which includes methane which is one of the most hazardous and powerful greenhouse gas contributing to the ozone layer depletion. In addition, the project would significantly reduce waste management costs for the city (citiesinvestmentfacility 2022). Therefore, by converting easily accessible waste materials into valuable renewable energy, we can establish a framework for an environmentally sustainable (Sahoo et.al. 2023) and circular economy in which waste is utilized as a resource rather than a liability. Despite having attained its culmination, the pursuit of sustainable energy alternatives through the utilization of underutilized resources such as waste persists, driven by the aspiration for an environmentally friendly future.

References

1. Abo, B. O., Gao, M., Wu, C., Zhu, W., & Wang, Q. (2019), "A review on characteristics of food waste and their use in butanol production", *Reviews on Environmental Health*, 34:447-457.
2. Streitwieser, D. A. (2017), "Comparison of the anaerobic digestion at the mesophilic and thermophilic temperature regime of organic wastes from the agribusiness", *Bioresource Technology*, 241:985-992.
3. Choudhary, A., Kumar, A., & Kumar, S. (2020), "Techno-economic analysis, kinetics, global warming potential comparison and optimization of a pilot-scale unheated semi-continuous anaerobic reactor in a hilly area: For north Indian hilly states", *Renewable Energy*, 155:1181-1190.
4. Chaudhary, P., Garg, S., George, T., Shabin, M., Saha, S., Subodh, S., & Sinha, B. (2021), "Underreporting and open burning—the two largest challenges for sustainable waste management in India", *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 175:105865.
5. Davison, N., Young, W., Ross, A., Cockerill, T., & Rajput, S. (2022), "Investigating the impacts of behavioural-change interventions and COVID-19 on the food-waste-generation behaviours of catered students in the UK and India", *Sustainability*, 14:5486.
6. Dhar, H., Kumar, P., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, S., & Vaidya, A. N. (2016), "Effect of organic loading rate during anaerobic digestion of municipal solid waste", *Bioresource Technology*, 217:56-61.
7. Dutta S, He M, Xiong X, Tsang DC (2021), "Sustainable management and recycling of food waste anaerobic digestate: a review", *Bioresour Technol*, 341:125915
8. FAO (2017) "The future of food and agriculture—trends and challenges. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations".
9. Gandhi, P., Kumar, S., Paritosh, K. et al. , "Hotel Generated Food Waste and Its Biogas Potential: A Case Study of Jaipur City, India", *Waste Biomass Valor* ,10:1459–1468.
10. Haldar D, Shabbirahmed AM, Singhanian RR, Chen CW, Dong CD, Ponnusamy VK, Patel AK,(2022), "Understanding the management of household food waste and its engineering for sustainable valorization- a state-of-the-art review", *Bioresour Technol*,12:7390
11. Ho KS, Chu LM (2019), "Characterization of food waste from different sources in Hong Kong", *Air Waste Manag Assoc*, 69(3):277–288
12. Kim E, Shin SG, Jannat MAH, Tongco JV, Hwang S ,(2017), "Use of food waste-recycling wastewater as an alternative carbon source for denitrification process- a full-scale study", *Bioresour Technol* 245:1016–1021
13. Kosmala M, Kołodziejczyk K, Zdunczyk Z, Juskiewicz J, Boros D (2011), "Chemical composition of natural and polyphenol-free apple pomace and the effect of this dietary ingredient on intestinal fermentation and serum lipid parameters in rats", *Jour Agri Food Chem*, 59:9177–9185
14. Li Y, Liu B, Song J, Jiang C, Yang Q (2015), "Utilization of potato starch processing wastes to produce animal feed with high lysine content", *Micro Biotech* 25:178–184
15. Li, Y., Jin, Y., Borrión, A., Li, H. and Li, J (2017), "Effects of organic composition on the anaerobic biodegradability of food waste", *Bioresource Technology*, 243, 836–845.
16. Mishra B, Varjani S, Pradhan I, Ekambaram N, Teixeira JA, Ngo HH, Guo W (2020), "Insights into interdisciplinary approaches for bioremediation of organic pollutants: innovations, challenges and perspectives", *Proc Nat Acad Sci: Bio Sci* 90:951–958.
17. Närvänen E, Mesiranta N, Mattila M, Heikkinen A (2020), "Introduction: a framework for managing food waste", *Food Waste Manag*, 1–24.

18. Obileke, K.C., Makaka, G. and Nwokolo, N (2023), “Recent Advancements in Anaerobic Digestion and Gasification Technology”, *Applied Sciences* , 13.
19. Paritosh, K., Kushwaha, S. K., Yadav, M., Pareek, N., Chawade, A., & Vivekanand, V. (2017), “Food waste to energy: an overview of sustainable approaches for food waste management and nutrient recycling”, *BioMed research international*, 2017:2370927.
20. Patricia Cunniff and Association of Official Analytical Chemists (1995) Official methods of analysis of AOAC international. 16th ed. Washington DC, Washington DC: Association of Official Analytical Chemists.
21. S Barik et al 2018 IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 167 012036
22. Sahoo, A., Dwivedi, A., Madheshiya, P., Kumar, U., Sharma, R. K., & Tiwari, S. (2024), “Insights into the management of food waste in developing countries: with special reference to India”, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31:17887-17913.
23. Sharma P, Gaur VK, Sirohi R, Varjani S, Kim SH, Wong JW (2021), “Sustainable processing of food waste for production of bio-based products for circular bioeconomy”, *Bioresour Technol*, 325:124684
24. Sluiter, A., Hames, B., Ruiz, R., Scarlata, C., Sluiter, J., Templeton, D., & Crocker, D. L. A. P. (2008), “Determination of structural carbohydrates and lignin in biomass”, *Laboratory analytical procedure*, 1617: 1-16.
25. Smithers GW (2008) Whey and whey proteins—From ‘gutter-to-gold.’ *Int Dairy J* 18:695–704
26. Uddin, M. M., & Wright, M. M. (2023), “Anaerobic digestion fundamentals, challenges, and technological advances”, *Physical Sciences Reviews*, 8:2819-2837.
27. United Nations (2015) Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 25 September 2015
28. Vidal, G., Carvalho, A., Endez, R.M. and Lema, J,M (2000), “Influence of the content in fats and proteins on the anaerobic biodegradability of dairy wastewaters”.
29. Wilkie, A,C (2005) *Anaerobic Digestion: Biology and Benefits*.
30. Yulin Ye (2013) *Biogas Production and Nutrient Recovery from Waste Streams*.